

Supplementary Materials

Removal of chromium species from low-contaminated raw water by different drinking water treatment processes

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S1. Species diagram of chromic acid in the pH range relevant to the study

Figure S1. Species diagram of chromic acid in the pH range relevant to the study.

S2. Full description for chemicals purity and suppliers

Substance	Supplier	Product numbers
Chromium (III) chloride heptahydrate, pure	Merck	2306348
Chromium (III) nitrate nonahydrate for analysis	Merck	1.02482
Potassium chromate for analysis	Merck	104952
Iron (II) sulfate heptahydrate for analysis	Merck	1.03965.0500
Hydrochloric acid 32%, Emsure	Merck	1.00319.2511
Sodium hydroxide 10%, Emsure	Merck	1.05588
Nitric acid 65%, suprapur	Merck	1.00456.1000
Ammonia solution 25%, suprapur	Merck	1.05428.0250
Chromium + 3 standard; 9.995 ± 0.049 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ Cr (III); 2% HNO ₃	SPETEC	J2-CR03106
Chromium + 6 standard; 10.000 ± 0.036 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Cr (VI), H ₂ O	SPETEC	H2-CR03100
SPETEC 169 calibration standard, 2% HNO ₃ , elements Cu, Zn, As, Ba, Co, Cr, Li, Ni, Pb, Se, Sr, Ti, Be, Ag, Cd, U	SPETEC	J2-MEB562067
SPETEC 170 calibration standard, 2% HNO ₃ , elements Al, Fe, Mn	SPETEC	J2-MEB562060
SPETEC 171 calibration standard, 2% HNO ₃ , elements Ca, Na, K, Mg, B	SPETEC	J2-MEB562065
SPETEC 172 calibration standard, 2% HNO ₃ , elements Si, P	SPETEC	J2-MEB562069
Deionized water, 18.2 M Ω /cm made with Purelab Classic	ELGA LabWater Veolia Water Technologies Deutschland GmbH, Celle, Germany	
Nitric acid, 65%, suprapur	Merck	1.00441
Sodium hydroxide 0.1 M	Merck	1.09141
Hydrochloric acid 0.1 M	Merck	1.09973
Active carbon Filtrasorb F300	Chemviron, Feluy, Belgium	
Active carbon Aquasorb F207	Chemviron, Feluy, Belgium	

S3. Chemical analysis of the raw water

Parameter ¹	Number of Analyses	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median
Temperature (°C)	36	11.0	13.8	12.5	12.4
pH	5	7.23	7.48	7.35	7.30
Oxygen (mg/L)	5	3.1	4.4	3.84	3.90
Electric conductivity (µS/cm)	36	710	862	760	761
Acidity to pH 8.2 (mmol/L)	2	0.36	0.53	0.45	0.45
Alkalinity to pH 4.3 (mmol/L)	5	3.12	3.40	3.24	3.22
Calcium (mg/L)	2	81.0	84.0	82.5	82.5
Magnesium (mg/L)	2	11.2	11.8	11.5	11.5
Sodium (mg/L)	2	46.4	51.8	49.1	49.1
Potassium	2	3.96	3.98	3.97	3.97
Ammonia (mg/L)	2	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.04
Iron (mg/L)	2	0.015	0.018	0.017	0.017
Manganese (mg/L)	2	0.015	0.018	0.017	0.017
Nitrate (mg/L)	5	11.6	15.6	12.9	11.9
Silicon dioxide (mg/L)	2	7.20	7.50	7.35	7.35
Sulphate (mg/L)	5	50.0	65.0	54.8	54.0
Chloride (mg/L)	5	87.0	125	104	101
Fluoride (mg/L)	5	0.05	0.13	0.11	0.12
Bromide (mg/L)	4	0.13	0.17	0.15	0.14
Phosphate total (mg/L)	2	0.050	0.100	0.075	0.075
Total organic carbon (mg/L)	2	0.81	0.94	0.88	0.88
Total plate count at 20 °C (cfu/mL)	35	0	0	0	0
Total plate count at 36 °C (cfu/mL)	35	0	3	0.26	0
Chromium (III) (µg/L) ²	3	<0.15	<0.15	<0.15	<0.15
Chromium (VI) (µg/L) ²	6	<0.25	0.28	0.24	0.26

¹ Methods employed were according to the German standard methods for the examination of water, wastewater and sludge.

² IC-ICP-MS according to the described method.

S4. A detailed description for the sampling points in the semi-technical pilot plant

Sampling point	Description	Remark
CAE	Aeration, storage tank	
CNFA	Inlet LPRO with antiscalant	
CNP1	Permeate pressure vessel 1	
CNP2	Permeate pressure vessel 2	
CNP3	Permeate pressure vessel 3	
CNP4	Permeate pressure vessel 4	
CNP	Collected permeate LPRO	
CNF1	Concentrate pressure vessel 1	
CNF2	Concentrate pressure vessel 2	
CNF3	Concentrate pressure vessel 3	
CNF4	Concentrate pressure vessel 4	
CO0	Inlet continuous flow reactor (CFR)	bottom
CO1	CFR, 1. sampling point	30 cm from bottom
CO2	CFR, 2. sampling point	60 cm from bottom
CO2	CFR, 3. sampling point	90 cm from bottom
CO4	CFR, 4. sampling point	120 cm from bottom
CO5	CFR, 5. sampling point	150 cm from bottom
CF1/1	Anthracite filter, 1. sampling point	30 cm from upper filter layer
CF1/2	Anthracite filter, 2. sampling point	60 cm from upper filter layer
CF1/3	Anthracite filter, 3. sampling point	90 cm from upper filter layer
CF1/4	Anthracite filter, 4. sampling point	120 cm from upper filter layer
CAF2	Drain anthracite filter, line 2	150 cm from upper filter layer
CAK2/1	ACF, 1. sampling point	50 cm from upper filter layer
CAK2/2	ACF, 2. sampling point	100 cm from upper filter layer
CAK2/3	ACF, 3. sampling point	150 cm from upper filter layer
CAK2/4	ACF, 4. sampling point	200 cm from upper filter layer
CAAK2	Drain ACF, line 2	250 cm from upper filter layer

S5. Specific operation data for LPRO

09.03.2016		Dosage of 10 µg/L chromium (III) chloride.		
Sampling point	pH value	Electric conductivity (µS/cm)	Temperature (°C)	
CFNA	7.77	740	12.8	
CNP1	7.04	23	12.9	
CNP2	6.42	36	13.0	
CNP3	6.03	41	13.1	
CNP4	5.77	33	13.1	
CNP	5.78	29	12.9	
CNF1	7.95	1,647	13.1	
CNF2	8.03	2,010	13.0	
CNF3	8.05	2,470	13.2	
CNF4	8.07	3,320	13.0	

09.03.2016		Dosage of 10 µg/L potassium chromate.		
Sampling point	pH value	Electric conductivity (µS/cm)	Temperature (°C)	
CFNA	7.68	755	12.9	
CNP1	6.89	25	13.0	
CNP2	6.51	38	13.1	
CNP3	4.41	22	13.1	
CNP4	5.50	35	13.2	
CNP	5.54	31	13.1	
CNF1	7.92	1,673	13.1	
CNF2	7.99	2,050	13.2	
CNF3	8.02	2,590	13.0	
CNF4	8.03	3,340	13.0	

16.03.2016		Dosage of 10 µg/L chromium (III) nitrate.		
Sampling point	pH value	Electric conductivity (µS/cm)	Temperature (°C)	
CFNA	7.67	763	13.0	
CNP1	-	27	13.1	
CNP2	-	39	13.1	
CNP3	-	24	13.1	
CNP4	-	37	13.1	
CNP	-	39	13.1	
CNF1	-	1,709	13.1	
CNF2	-	2,080	13.1	
CNF3	-	2,580	13.2	

CNF4	-	3,430	13.1
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Date	09.03.2016	16.03.2016	01.06.2016	01.06.2016
Time	09:00	09:15	09:30	12:15
Inflow (L/h)	1679	1688	1692	1697
Permeate flow (L/h)	1398	1400	1404	1400
Concentrate flow (L/h)	281	288	288	297
Flow recirculation (L/h)	441	447	451	445
Yield (%)	83.3	82.9	83	82.5
Electric conductivity, collected permeate ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	32	35	52	62
Electric conductivity inflow ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	736	781	760	827
Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	13	13	13	13
Raw water pressure (bar)	2	1.9	2.0	2.0
Operating pressure (bar)	6.6	6.7	6.8	6.6
Concentrate pressure (bar)	5.4	5.4	5.4	5.3
Differential pressure (bar)	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.4
Concentrate pressure 4. vessel (bar)	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.4
Electric conductivity 4. vessel ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	37	40	62	75
pH value inflow	7.50	7.40	6.48	5.55
pH value concentrate	7.90	7.90	7.20	6.60
Antiscalant ($\text{g P}/\text{m}^3$)	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21
Permeate flows				
Vessel 1 (L/h)	420	420	420	420
Vessel 2 (L/h)	370	370	370	370
Vessel 3 (L/h)	300	300	300	300
Vessel 4 (L/h)	300	300	300	300
Sum (L/h)	1390	1390	1390	1390

16.03.2016	Dosage of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ potassium chromate, pH 7.6.			
Sampling point	pH value	Electric conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Oxygen (mg/l)
CFNA	7.58	765	12.9	10.6
CNP1	7.42	30	13.2	10.5
CNP2	6.71	38	13.1	10.5
CNP3	6.64	23	13.1	10.5
CNP4	6.10	36	13.2	10.5

CNP	6.02	31	13.2	10.5
CNF1	7.59	1,708	13.1	10.5
CNF2	7.75	2,090	13.2	10.6
CNF3	7.80	2,590	13.3	10.6
CNF4	7.87	3,410	13.3	10.6

01.06.2016

Dosage of 10 µg/L potassium chromate, pH 8.3.

Sampling point	pH value	Electric conductivity (µS/cm)	Temperature (°C)	Oxygen (mg/l)
CFNA	8.3	707	15.0	9.4
CNP1	-	24	15.3	-
CNP2	-	38	15.3	-
CNP3	-	30	15.6	-
CNP4	-	42	15.4	-
CNP	-	32	14.9	-

S6. Analytical characteristics of UV/VIS-method for Cr (VI) at 375 nm

Calibration parameters	Cr (VI)	Cr (VI)
	5 cm cuvette	1 cm cuvette
Calibration range (mmol/L)	0.004 - 0.04	0.015 – 0.15
Detection limit LOD (mmol/L)	0.0013	0.065
Limit of quantitation LOQ (mmol/L)	0.007	0.20
Variation coefficient of method (%)	1.6	1.2
Correlation coefficient	0.9990	0.9980

S7. Analytical characteristics of chromium and iron analytics with ICP-MS

Calibration parameters	Chromium, total	Chromium, total, low concentra- tion	Iron, total
Calibration range (µg/L)	2-60	0.05-2.00	25-300
Detection limit LOD (µg/L)	0.5	0.05	6.7
Limit of quantitation LOQ (µg/L)	1.2	0.15	20
Variation coefficient of method (%)	1.6	1.2	1.2
Correlation coefficient	0.9990	0.9978	0.9990

S8. Relative combined uncertainties for analytics with ICP-MS

Parameter	Relative combined uncertainty (%)
Boron	6.6
Sodium	6.9
Magnesium	4.5
Silica	5.7
Phosphate, total	9.9
Potassium	5.7
Calcium	6.1
Chromium (III) / (VI) / total	6.5
Iron	5.7

S9. Analytical characteristics and chromatogram of Cr (III) / Cr (VI) speciation method with IC-ICP-MS

Calibration parameters	Cr (III)	Cr (VI)
Calibration range ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	0.1- 1.0	0.1- 1.0
Sensitivity (Counts/ μg)	40328 \pm 1491	41525 \pm 2684
Residual standard deviation (Counts)	587	987
Detection limit LOD($\mu\text{g/L}$)	0.033	0.055
Limit of quantitation LOQ ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	0.15	0.25
Variation coefficient of method (%)	2.65	4.55
Correlation coefficient	0.9990	0.9974

S10. Acid treatment of multiple reactivated activated charcoal

Extracted elements	Extract of 0.5 g of reactivated F300 with 60 ml of 10% HCl (mg/L)
Aluminum (mg/L)	10
Barium (mg/L)	1.1
Calcium (mg/L)	58
Chromium (mg/L)	2.6
Copper (mg/L)	1.6
Iron (mg/L)	40
Magnesium (mg/l)	5.1
Manganese (mg/L)	0.74
Nickel (mg/L)	1.4
Phosphate (mg/L)	4.7
Potassium (mg/L)	1.2
Sodium (mg/L)	131

S11. Detailed numerical data on chromium removal in the ACF line

11.02.2016		Dosage of 10 µg/L potassium chromate and 10 µg/L chromium (III) chloride.	
Sampling point	Chromium (VI) (µg/l)	Chromium (III) (µg/l)	
CAE	<0.25	<0.15	
CO0	12.73	0.77	
CO1	12.69	0.79	
CO2	12.05	0.85	
CO3	12.10	0.75	
CO4	12.89	0.83	
CO5	13.03	0.88	
CF2/1	12.89	0.19	
CF2/2	12.88	<0.15	
CF2/3	13.35	<0.15	
CF2/4	12.26	<0.15	
CAF2	12.24	<0.15	
CAK2/1	11.33	<0.15	
CAK2/2	8.72	<0.15	
CAK2/3	5.47	<0.15	
CAK2/4	3.73	<0.15	
CAAK2	3.58	<0.15	

Specific load 29.5 m³/kg

11.04.2016		Dosage of 10 µg/L potassium chromate and 10 µg/L chromium (III) nitrate.		
Sampling point	Chromium (VI) (µg/l)	Chromium (III) (µg/l)	Chromium total (µg/l)	
CO0	10.84	2.79	16.10	
CO1	11.29	3.07	17.47	
CO2	11.08	3.50	17.65	
CO3	11.26	3.38	16.86	
CO4	11.33	3.45	18.13	
CO5	10.95	3.30	17.86	
CF2/1	14.55	0.41	15.07	
CF2/2	14.86	0.23	14.83	
CF2/3	14.79	<0.15	14.78	
CF2/4	14.96	<0.15	14.40	
CAF2	14.94	<0.15	14.31	
CAK2/1	15.12	<0.15	14.38	
CAK2/2	12.12	<0.15	11.45	
CAK2/3	9.29	<0.15	8.90	
CAK2/4	6.26	<0.15	5.63	
CAAK2	5.69	<0.15	5.63	

Specific load 38.5 m³/kg

11.05.2016		Dosage of 1 µg/L potassium chromate and 1 µg/L chromium (III) nitrate.		
Sampling point	Chromium (VI) (µg/l)	Chromium (III) (µg/l)	Chromium total (µg/l)	
CO0	1.42	<0.15	1.51	
CAF2	1.23	<0.15	1.18	
CAK2/1	1.06	<0.15	1.07	
CAK2/2	0.83	<0.15	0.78	
CAK2/3	0.60	<0.15	0.61	
CAK2/4	0.50	<0.15	0.41	
CAAK2	0.43	<0.15	0.54	

Specific load 43.0 m³/kg

14.03.2017		Dosage of 10 µg/L potassium chromate.	
Sampling point	Chromium total (µg/L)		
CAF2	9.2		
CAK 2/1	9.1		
CAK 2/2	7.9		
CAK 2/3	6.2		
CAK 2/4	4.1		
CAAK 2	2.3		

Specific load 86.5 m³/kg

S12. Cr (VI) adsorption on full-scale AC filters

Specific load (m ³ /kg)	Removal AC Norit (%)	Removal AC Chemviron (%)	Supplier
4.29		51.6	Chemviron F300
13.42		7.3	Chemviron F300
4.90	35.8		Norit GAC 830
18.51	-24.0		Norit GAC 830
0.83		28.0	Chemviron F300
0.47		27.2	Chemviron F300
5.09		26.0	Chemviron F300
26.33		-12.1	Chemviron F300
13.38	18.3		Norit GAC 830
6.25		33.9	Chemviron F300
15.23		-28.8	Chemviron F300
4.84	42.8		Norit GAC 830
15.60	-23.4		Norit GAC 830
12.28	-14.5		Norit GAC 830
14.45		17.1	Chemviron F300
3.52		37.6	Chemviron F300
3.64	31.0		Norit GAC 830
9.08	37.3		Norit GAC 830
2.04		35.7	Chemviron F300

S13. Analytical data for the chromium removal with RCF treatment

20.04.2016 Dosage of 10 µg/L potassium chromate with 6 mg/L ferrous sulphate.		
Sampling point	Chromium, total (µg/L)	Iron (mg/L)
Raw water	0.28	<0.02
CAE	12.2	<0.02
CO1, filtered	0.57	0.41
CO2, filtered	<0.15	0.38
CO3, filtered	<0.15	0.31
CO4, filtered	<0.15	0.36
CO5, filtered	<0.15	0.26
CAF2	<0.15	<0.02

Temperature 14.6 °C, oxygen 8.52 mg/L.

11.05.2016 Dosage of 1 µg/L potassium chromate with 2 mg/L ferrous sulphate.			
Sampling point	Chromium (VI) (µg/l)	Chromium (III) (µg/l)	Chromium total (µg/l)
CAE	1.42	-	1.51
CO1, filtered	-	-	0.17
CO2, filtered	-	-	<0.15
CO3, filtered	-	-	<0.15
CO4, filtered	-	-	<0.15
CO5, filtered	-	-	<0.15
CF2/1	<0.25	<0.15	0.52
CF2/2	<0.25	<0.15	0.47
CF2/3	<0.25	<0.15	0.22
CF2/4	<0.25	<0.15	<0.15
CAF2	<0.25	<0.15	<0.15

Temperature 16.3 °C, oxygen 8.80 mg/L.

19.05.2016 Dosage of 10 µg/L potassium chromate with 1 mg/L ferrous sulphate			
Sampling point	Chromium (VI) (µg/l)	Chromium (III) (µg/l)	Chromium total (µg/l)
CAE	10.5	<0.15	10.5
CO1, filtered	0.35	<0.15	0.40
CO2, filtered	0.98	<0.15	0.95
CO3, filtered	0.20	<0.15	0.21
CO4, filtered	<0.25	<0.15	0.18
CO5, filtered	<0.25	<0.15	0.19
CF2/1	<0.25	0.25	1.98
CF2/2	<0.25	0.15	0.97
CF2/3	<0.25	<0.15	1.22
CF2/4	0.25	<0.15	0.41
CAF2	0.26	<0.15	0.30

Temperature 15.4 °C, oxygen 9.06 mg/L.

19.05.2016 Dosage of 10 µg/L potassium chromate with 2 mg/L ferrous sulphate.

Sampling point	Chromium total (µg/l)
CAE	10.5
CO1, filtered	<0.15
CO2, filtered	<0.15
CO3, filtered	<0.15
CO4, filtered	<0.15
CO5, filtered	<0.15
CF2/1	2.11
CF2/2	2.16
CF2/3	0.39
CF2/4	0.22
CAF2	<0.15

Temperature 15.6 °C, oxygen 9.00 mg/L.

S14. Detailed analytical data for elements during LPRO trials

For LPRO operation data see S4.

09.03.2016		Dosage of 10 µg/L chromium (III) chloride, pH 7.7.		
Sampling point	Sodium (mg/l)	Calcium (mg/l)	Chromium (III) (µg/l)	
CNFA	48.4	81.6	11.6	
CNP1	4.20	<2	0.23	
CNP2	6.32	<2	0.16	
CNP3	3.84	<2	<0.15	
CNP4	5.92	<2	<0.15	
CNP	5.22	<2	0.29	
CNF1	113	190	21.4	
CNF2	134	254	28.1	
CNF3	178	281	30.7	
CNF4	249	412	48.7	

09.03.2016		Dosage of 10 µg/L potassium chromate, pH 7.7.		
Sampling point	Sodium (mg/l)	Calcium (mg/l)	Chromium (VI) (µg/l)	
CNFA	50.5	80.9	13.7	
CNP1	4.36	<2	<0.25	
CNP2	6.64	<2	<0.25	
CNP3	3.93	<2	<0.25	
CNP4	6.26	<2	<0.25	
CNP	5.51	<2	<0.25	
CNF1	118	194	28.5	
CNF2	142	222	36.5	
CNF3	192	322	40.4	
CNF4	261	436	59.7	

16.03.2016		Dosage of 10 µg/L chromium (III) nitrate, pH 7.4.		
Sampling point	Sodium (mg/l)	Calcium (mg/l)	Chromium (III) (µg/l)	
CNFA	44.3	87.8	10.3	
CNP1	4.13	<2	<0.15	
CNP2	6.52	<2	<0.15	
CNP3	5.27	<2	<0.15	
CNP4	6.30	<2	<0.15	
CNP	5.31	<2	<0.15	
CNF1	109	242	20.9	
CNF2	136	292	31.9	
CNF3	167	350	32.3	
CNF4	245	503	47.5	

16.03.2016		Dosage of 10 µg/L potassium chromate, pH 7.6.		
Sampling point	Sodium (mg/l)	Calcium (mg/l)	Chromium (VI) (µg/l)	
CNFA	44.6	86.0	10.4	
CNP1	4.43	<2	<0.25	
CNP2	6.50	<2	<0.25	
CNP3	4.14	<2	<0.25	
CNP4	6.43	<2	<0.25	
CNP	5.41	<2	0.26	
CNF1	118	251	25.8	
CNF2	142	300	34.0	
CNF3	176	359	41.5	
CNF4	235	464	52.8	

01.06.2016		Dosage of 10 µg/L potassium chromate, pH 6.5.		
Sampling point	Sodium (mg/l)	Calcium (mg/l)	Chromium (VI) (µg/l)	
CNFA	45.0	81.5	9.55	
CNP1	5.24	<2	<0.25	
CNP2	7.70	<2	<0.25	
CNP3	6.19	<2	<0.25	
CNP4	8.98	<2	<0.25	
CNP	7.18	<2	<0.25	
CNF1	107	204	23.9	
CNF2	128	258	28.0	
CNF3	174	328	40.1	
CNF4	232	453	50.9	

01.06.2016		Dosage of 10 µg/L potassium chromate, pH 5.6.		
Sampling point	Sodium (mg/l)	Calcium (mg/l)	Chromium (VI) (µg/l)	
CNFA	46.6	80.7	9.51	
CNP1	7.15	<2	<0.25	
CNP2	9.59	<2	0.34	
CNP3	11.5	<2	0.29	
CNP4	8.99	<2	0.30	
CNP	9.03	<2	0.25	
CNF1	106	211	25.6	
CNF2	130	265	31.4	
CNF3	167	310	36.1	
CNF4	231	429	51.6	

01.06.2016 Dosage of 10 µg/L potassium chromate, pH 8.3.

Sampling point	Sodium (mg/l)	Calcium (mg/l)	Chromium (VI) (µg/l)
CNFA	51.00	81.6	9.42
CNP1	4.44	<2	<0.25
CNP2	6.78	<2	<0.25
CNP3	4.94	<2	<0.25
CNP4	7.19	<2	<0.25
CNP	5.88	<2	<0.25
CNF1	123.08	214	25.1
CNF2	154.70	260	27.7
CNF3	196.92	325	37.9
CNF4	280.38	474	58.6

S15. Stability of Cr (III) in raw water

Experiment

Raw water (250 ml, pH 7.46, 685 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, 24 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) was stirred with 100 rpm and the turbidity was measured for 30 min. After 3 min. chromium (III) chloride or nitrate solution in deionized water was added to get a starting concentration of 0.04 mM Cr (III). The raw water without Cr (III) was measured as a reference. The experiment was repeated at Cr (III) concentrations of 10 and 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$.

Results

No increase in turbidity was found in raw water. After an initiation phase of some minutes, the addition of Cr (III) leads to a sharp increase in turbidity, with chromium (III) chloride and chromium (III) nitrate behaving very similarly. At lower concentrations, particle formation can be assured at a concentration of 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$. It can be assumed that chromium hydroxide was formed.

Figure S2a. Turbidity increase by of 0.04 mM Cr (III) in raw water.

Figure S2b. Turbidity increase by 10 and 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ Cr (III) in raw water; arrows indicate time of dosage.